

Traditional Practices in Maternal and Infant Care Among Women in Rural Area: A Case Study in North 24 Parganas District of West Bengal

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In many parts of the world, customs and beliefs from the past impact and encourage the behaviour of women during pregnancy and childbirth. In India, maternity experiences used to be shaped by a variety of cultural traditions. Traditionally in India, pregnancy is considered as a matter which barely requires clinical intervention. Even some decades ago, the family members of a pregnant women used to consult a doctor in case of an extreme emergency issue.

Certain cultural beliefs, rituals, and traditions in India about pregnancy, childbirth, and child development have their roots in the knowledge found in ancient Indian books. In India, traditions such as planning a feast for a social gathering are prevalent throughout all regions, religions, castes, and socioeconomic classes, and West Bengal is no exception.

The postpartum experience in West Bengal is greatly influenced by different practices associated with prolonged breastfeeding, food restrictions, and solitude following childbirth. In addition, customs like bathing babies, keeping the umbilical stump clean, and postpartum home confinement are examples of the deeply ingrained customs that influence mother care in this area. During their pregnancies, deliveries, and postpartum periods, many Indian women adhere to these particular customs. In order to give women with culturally competent treatment and support during the crucial postpartum time, healthcare professionals must have a thorough understanding of these traditional beliefs and behaviours.

The primary aim of this paper is to make an account of the practices in relation to recommendations made by contemporary healthcare professionals. The paper also aims to see the degree to which pregnant women in rural areas of North 24 Pargana still follow the customary taboos and practices during pregnancy, postpartum recovery, and infant feeding. A group of mothers of different communities, caste from different socio-economic backgrounds were interviewed from 4 sub divisions of North 24 Pargana to observe these traditional practices and beliefs still influence the customary taboos and practices during pregnancy, postpartum recovery, and infant feeding.

Keywords: Traditional Practices, Postpartum, Healthcare professional, Cultural belief, Childbirth